

Project report for Moore Foundation

This is the final project report for the grant *Binder on JupyterHub: Containers for Reproducible Research and Publication*. It covers each of the suggested questions from the Moore foundation, and tries to provide context for the main deliverables and success stories from the project. We'll list each question below, and our answers to it in-line.

Your project's progress in the last year, especially as compared to your stated outputs/tasks

Below we will address each of the stated goals / outputs in the original proposal for the Moore foundation, and discuss progress that has been made on each one.

Primary outcome: Easy, reproducible workflows are available via Binder for scientists to deploy containers with Python, R, and Julia environments.

Output 1.1: New technical features enhance the experience of using Binder for reproducible computational workflows.

1.1.1 Provide user-facing UI for statistics and Binder health monitoring

The BinderHub deployment at mybinder.org now has a public Grafana dashboard that displays usage information about user activity, repository launches, etc. This dashboard is accessible at <https://grafana.mybinder.org>, and is replicable / deployable for other BinderHub deployments as well. The configuration for this dashboard can be found here: <https://github.com/jupyterhub/mybinder.org-deploy/blob/master/mybinder/values.yaml#L328>.

1.1.2 Support use of Binder with applications that complement the Jupyter stack (JupyterLab/Notebook), such as RStudio, etc.

There have been a number of improvements in the Binder ecosystem for supporting non-Jupyter user interfaces. The most generic of these is the repository “jupyter-server-proxy” (<https://github.com/jupyterhub/jupyter-server-proxy>), which allows developers to proxy arbitrary applications that can run by a web interface through a JupyterHub. This has been used to expose many user interfaces via a BinderHub, for example, RStudio and Shiny interfaces (<https://github.com/binder-examples/r>) or document authoring interfaces such as Stencila (<https://github.com/binder-examples/stencila-multi>)

1.1.3 Create technical solutions towards connecting Binder instances with data that is stored outside of the repository.

The story around connecting data sources with a BinderHub is still evolving. There are no official tools that the Binder community has created for this, largely because it's a problem space we think is best-suited to tools from other communities (Binder doesn't want to strictly be in the business of handling data curation, I/O, etc, it wants to enable best-practices from the communities as they are developed).

The Binder team has addressed this issue thus far by partnering with others in the community who have their own data tools and solutions. We have created documentation and examples for many of these tools. Below are a few example repositories.

- <https://github.com/binder-examples/getting-data>
- <https://github.com/binder-examples/data-quilt>
- https://github.com/binder-examples/remote_storage
- <https://github.com/binder-examples/getting-data-xroot>

Output 1.2: Binder user community has increased in size and diversity.

1.2.1 Create documentation and training materials for bootcamps on teaching scientists how to create / deploy Binder-compliant repositories.

The Binder team has run several bootcamps and training materials on creating your own Binder-ready repositories. We now have documentation on creating your own Binder repository on the Binder user documentation (<https://mybinder.readthedocs.io/en/latest/introduction.html>). There have also been efforts from others in the community to create their own documentation and tools for easily building Binder-ready repositories. For example, the Holepunch project (<https://github.com/karthik/holepunch>) provides an R interface to easily build Binder-ready repositories that build off of the Rocker stack of Docker images. In addition, the Turing Way project, a community-driven handbook for best-practices in open research, has included a section and several tutorials on using Binder (https://the-turing-way.netlify.com/reproducible_environments/04/binder.html).

1.2.2 Host several Binder training sessions / workshops to increase adoption and community input

Members of the Binder team have hosted several workshops and training sessions over the past year. These include presentations and tutorials at SciPy, NeurIPS, the MLOSS conference, a workshop at the University of Washington on reproducibility, many workshops at UC Berkeley, Research Bazaar at University of Oslo, and a two-day workshop at UC Davis.

1.2.3 Add a gallery of canonical examples as Binder repositories for each language. Include a set of “Binder-compliant practices” in each language to demo w/ Binder.

We have a list of examples of Binder usage hosted on GitHub (<https://github.com/binder-examples>). In addition, the documentation now has a list of these repositories, and short explanations for the kind of environment they build (https://mybinder.readthedocs.io/en/latest/sample_repos.html).

1.2.4 Support novel interactive publications through collaboration with publishers (eLife, mSystems, etc)

The Binder project has interfaced with other projects directed specifically at scientific publishing. First, eLife’s recent open publishing platform is powered by mybinder.org (<https://elifesciences.org/labs/d42fe2b9/integrating-binder-and-stencila-the-building-blocks-to-increased-open-communication-and-transparency> and <https://elifesciences.org/labs/ad58f08d/introducing-elife-s-first-computationally-reproducible-article>). In addition, repo2docker (and thus BinderHub) now supports links that point to Zenodo DOIs (<https://blog.jupyter.org/binder-with-zenodo-af68ed6648a6>), allowing individuals to run Zenodo repositories on a BinderHub. Finally, a team of neuroscientists in Canada has developed the NeuroLibre project, an open publishing platform that uses BinderHub as the core engine for interactive environments and reproducibility (<https://conp-pcno.github.io/>).

1.2.5 Collect use-case information in order to develop a roadmap to meet new demands for future development.

As part of this grant, the Binder team helped create the Jupyter Community Forum (<https://discourse.jupyter.org/c/binder>). This has become a public space for conversation, questions, brainstorming, and sharing thoughts around the Binder project. In addition, the Binder team has been holding regular monthly meetings for the broader community to participate (<https://jupyterhub-team-compass.readthedocs.io/en/latest/meetings.html>). We have had guests from other open source projects, companies, universities, and publishers, and have used these meetings to feed new ideas into roadmaps for future development (<https://jupyterhub-team-compass.readthedocs.io/en/latest/milestones.html>).

Output 1.3: mybinder.org is sustainable

1.3.1 Increase the computational resource available to the public binder to support higher levels of usage

The core effort for sustainability in the Binder project has been the development of underlying open source tools that power mybinder.org. By making these tools open and vendor/cloud-agnostic, we increase the number of organizational stakeholders that can feed resources into the technology (for example, the CONP team from NeuroLibre, the Turing Institute, or eLife).

In addition, the Binder team recently partnered with OVH (a France-based cloud company) to federate mybinder.org across two BinderHub deployments. OVH runs and maintains a

BinderHub for public use at ovh.mybinder.org (similar to the one that the Binder team has been maintaining, which now lives at gke.mybinder.org). We believe this is a model that can be replicated with new institutional partners, such that the cost of running and maintaining the public mybinder.org service can be shared with these organizations. See <https://blog.jupyter.org/the-international-binder-federation-4f6235c1537e> for more information.

1.3.2 Fund sustainable deployment and maintenance of mybinder.org (e.g., compute me, personnel me for issue triage and incident response)

The resources from this grant allowed for the development of many new pieces of Binder technology (particularly BinderHub and repo2docker) and allowed these communities to grow in both users and developers. In particular, this funding helped support the work of expanding governance and contribution materials, which have made it easier and more attractive to contribute to the ecosystem, which can be seen in the increase in the Binder and JupyterHub team sizes, as well as the number of general contributors.

1.3.3 series of blog posts throughout the year documenting the pilot findings

Below is a list of blog posts that the Binder team has written over the last year and a half:

- Binder 2.0: <https://blog.jupyter.org/binder-2-0-a-tech-guide-2017-fd40515a3a84?source=false-----0>
- Binder and Zenodo integration: <https://blog.jupyter.org/binder-with-zenodo-af68ed6648a6?source=false-----1>
- The Binder federation: <https://blog.jupyter.org/the-international-binder-federation-4f6235c1537e?source=false-----2>
- Stencila integration with Binder: <https://blog.jupyter.org/elif-sprint-integrating-stencila-and-binder-18834e9ad584?source=false-----3>
- BinderHub out of beta: <https://blog.jupyter.org/binderhub-is-out-of-beta-fa2781a229d6?source=false-----4>
- Release of repo2docker: <https://blog.jupyter.org/introducing-repo2docker-61a593c0752d?source=false-----5>
- Binder serves two million launches: <https://blog.jupyter.org/mybinder-org-serves-two-million-launches-7543ae498a2a?source=false-----6>
- Mybinder.org automated upgrades bot: <https://blog.jupyter.org/automating-mybinder-org-dependency-upgrades-in-10-steps-bb5e38542059?source=false-----7>

1.3.4 Establish governance model with clear guidelines for participation, in service of long-term mission.

The Binder project has established a governance and onboarding process that it maintains in the “JupyterHub Team Compass” repository: <https://jupyterhub-team-compass.readthedocs.io/en/latest/binder/governance.html>

Output 1.4: Binder deployments other than the public Binder are actively used

There are several other deployments of the BinderHub software that we know of. The first public BinderHub deployed by another team is <https://notebooks.gesis.org/binder/>. This instance is operated by a team from the GESIS Institute fuer Sozialwissenschaften in Germany. The Pangeo project runs a public BinderHub to provide their cloud platform for earth analytics. The Turing Institute runs a BinderHub as a part of their “Turing Way” project for reproducible science. Finally, a team at OVH runs the public BinderHub that is part of the “mybinder.org” federation. In addition, eLife and Stencila as well as the NeuroLibre team are actively exploring the use of BinderHub for reproducible publishing platforms.

Several companies also operate BinderHubs for internal use.

1.4.1 Develop infrastructure metrics and logging for deployments

BinderHub now has the ability to expose a public data stream of Binder launch activity over time. This exists for the mybinder.org BinderHub deployments at <https://archive.analytics.mybinder.org>.

1.4.2 Allow users to deploy Binder locally from binder-compliant repositories.

We have designed repo2docker (the underlying tool that BinderHub uses for environment generation) to be runnable in any environment that has Docker. It is possible to use repo2docker locally to create an interactive environment that can be explored within a Docker container, and many have reported using it to ensure that their work is reproducible outside the context of Binder.

1.4.3 Create documentation and instructions for deploying custom Binder servers via JupyterHub

The Binder team has created extensive documentation on running one’s own BinderHub deployment at <https://binderhub.readthedocs.io>. In addition, we have included documentation on running repo2docker in the context of a JupyterHub in order to build reproducible environments: <https://zero-to-jupyterhub.readthedocs.io/en/latest/repo2docker.html>. Finally, we have partnered with Microsoft to make a BinderHub deployable on Azure with a single click:

<https://techcommunity.microsoft.com/t5/Educator-Developer-Blog/Deploying-BinderHub-onto-Microsoft-Azure/ba-p/687974>.

Changes to your original stated outputs/tasks

There were no major unexpected changes to the project's original outputs and tasks. The biggest change that happened was a shift in our understanding of what Binder should and should not do. Over time, we gained a better understanding of which parts of "open, reproducible, sharable environments" we should handle with new technology, and which we rely on other projects to use. For example, we decided not to explicitly handle data I/O, and instead allow others to determine which tools suited them best for this task. We may revisit these in the future as the landscape of tools for open science continues to evolve.

Any challenges/opportunities encountered

The biggest challenge for our team has been in sustaining ongoing "core-team" development in the absence of any new sources of funding. In many ways the Binder project has been much more successful than we originally envisioned. When this grant was first submitted, mybinder.org was launching approximately 3,000 user sessions each month. Now, mybinder.org runs nearly 350,000 sessions each month, a factor of 100 increase. In that time, the amount of resources available to both run the BinderHub at mybinder.org and develop new technology for Binder has not increased.

Any personnel changes (additions, departures, etc)

All of the members of the original Binder team are still a part of the project, though some have moved on to other roles in their professional careers and spend either a percentage of their time on Binder, or contribute as a side project. In particular, Carol Willing is now an independent contractor and works part-time at Quansight, and Tim Head now works at a start-up in Switzerland and contributes to Binder in his spare time. We also supported two other members of the Jupyter Project - Lindsey Heagy and Ian Rose - who were doing domain-specific work in documentation, training, and interactive notebooks for Binder.

Evidence of awareness/recognition of your project. No need to re-list things on the spreadsheet; use this space for anecdotal stories of the broader impacts of this grant

As mentioned earlier, we have been surprised at the considerable impact and usage that the Binder project has had on the scientific, educational, and broader data science community. "Sharing a Binder" is now a common-place term in many online communities, and we have seen a large growth in the number of sessions being launched on Binder, and unique repositories that are Binder-ready. Binder is a common tool for tutorials and training sessions, and has become a staple at many technical conferences (for example, the Binder team noticed a clear bump in the Grafana charts when the SciPy 2019 tutorials were being run).

Your expenditures over the last year. Please explain variances >20%. **This information is supplemental to the updated budget described below.**

There haven't been any unexpected expenditures over the course of this grant - the large majority have gone into paying developer time for the Binder core team. The biggest shift in expenses came in the form of cloud computing costs. This was initially because work was done to make BinderHub more efficient and less resource-intensive in the public mybinder.org instance, and later because Google Cloud gave us a year's worth of credits to run mybinder.org. This allowed us to support more core developer time off of this grant.

How can we help you? What can we do to facilitate your work?

The biggest thing we need help with right now is in thinking about sustainability and continued growth of the project. As mentioned above, the Binder project is currently not supported by any direct funding, even though it is now running a large public service with nearly 350,000 users per month. The project has done a good job to ensure that it will sustain itself through its open community moving forward (both on the development side as well as on the deployment side). However, dedicated funding and assistance with planning around future sustainability will position the project for more technical improvements and community growth in the future, particularly as the cloud services world becomes more saturated with corporate offerings.